
ANALYSIS OF THE ROLE OF 112 SERVICES IN HANDLING CONFLICT BASED ON PUBLIC REPORTS IN THE COMMUNICATION AND INFORMATICS SERVICE OF MANADO CITY

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Abstract

This study analyzes the role of the 112 Service of the Manado City Communication and Informatics Office in handling social conflicts based on public reports and identifies factors that influence its effectiveness. This study uses a qualitative approach with the interactive analysis method of Miles, Huberman, and Saldana (2019). Data were obtained through in-depth interviews with key informants from the Manado City Communication and Informatics Office, related agencies, and the community, supported by field observations and documentation studies. The results indicate that the 112 Service has played a strategic role as a mechanism for receiving reports, inter-agency coordination, and early control of social conflicts. However, this role is still reactive and facilitative, not fully proactive and executive. The early warning system still relies on direct reports from the public, and inter-agency coordination is still carried out manually. The effectiveness of the service is influenced by five main factors: institutional aspects, human resources, work systems and procedures, information technology support, and inter-agency coordination. These five factors together form a gap between the ideal concept of modern public services and their actual implementation in the field.

Keywords: 112 Service, Social Conflict Management, E-Government, Early Warning System, Cross-Agency Coordination

INTRODUCTION

Manado City, as the center of government, economic, and social activities in North Sulawesi Province, is characterized by a heterogeneous society with a high level of urban life dynamics. Intense social interactions in public spaces, residential areas, and daily economic activities create the potential for various social problems. Disputes between residents, disturbances to neighborhood order, crime, domestic violence, and even the potential for horizontal conflict often arise from simple issues that, if not promptly addressed, can escalate into broader conflicts and disrupt social stability (Manado City Communications and Information Office, 2018). In these conditions, the public needs an official channel to report the problems they face, as well as assurance that these reports will be followed up quickly and professionally by government officials. Responding to these needs, the Manado City Government, through the Communication and Information Agency, initiated the Manado Siaga 112 service as an information technology-based public service innovation. This service is designed to facilitate the public in submitting emergency reports, security disturbances, and social conflicts through a single integrated call number. Conceptually, the 112 service is expected to be the frontline in the early warning system for handling conflicts based on public reports in Manado City (Manado City Communication and Information Agency, 2018). Based on the characteristics of public reports received through the Manado Siaga 112 service, it can be identified that this service not only functions as an emergency complaint channel, but also as an important instrument in handling social conflicts based on public reports, covering various forms of conflict ranging from security and order disturbances, social conflicts between residents, to information-based conflicts that

develop in the digital space. Data from the Manado City Communications and Information Office (2025) shows that 670 reports related to conflict and social disturbances were recorded. The most dominant type of report was disturbances to security and order with 215 reports (32.1%), reflecting the high public demand for a rapid response from authorities in emergency situations and the potential for open conflict. Social conflict between residents ranked second with 148 reports (22.1%), indicating that horizontal conflict at the community level remains a significant problem. Reports related to disturbances to public order reached 121 reports (18.1%), domestic violence (KDRT) with 96 reports (14.3%), information-based or digital conflicts with 54 reports (8.1%), and reports of potential conflict with 36 reports (5.3%). This diversity of report types indicates that social conflict in Manado City has complex and heterogeneous characteristics, thus requiring the readiness of an adaptive and integrated service system. However, in practice, the 112 service faces various challenges. Incoming public reports vary in terms of urgency, type of conflict, and complexity of handling. Conflicts based on public reports often require cross-sector coordination, including those between the police, civil service police units, health departments, and other regional agencies. Unprepared coordination systems or limited response capacity can lead to delays in handling and potentially escalate conflicts (Dwiyanto, 2017). Furthermore, although the 112 service has been operational and received various recognitions as a public service innovation, there are still public perceptions of delayed responses, unclear follow-up actions on reports, and weak coordination among regional agencies in conflict management. This situation indicates a gap between the objectives of the 112 service policy and its implementation in practice, particularly in the context of handling social conflicts based on public reports.

From a public administration perspective, this condition emphasizes that public services are a concrete manifestation of the state's presence in people's lives. Public services are not merely understood as administrative activities, but as a process of fulfilling citizens' basic rights, including the right to security, order, and protection from potential social conflict. The quality of public services is a direct reflection of the government's capacity to carry out government functions that are responsive, effective, and oriented towards the interests of the wider community (Hardiansyah, 2018). As the modern public administration paradigm develops, the government is required to shift its service approach from one that is procedural and bureaucratic to one that is participatory, responsive, and based on community needs. The *New Public Service paradigm* emphasizes that the public is not merely a customer, but a citizen *who* has the right to be heard, involved, and served fairly (Denhardt & Denhardt, 2015).

The development of information and communication technology is increasingly driving the transformation of public service delivery through the implementation of *the e-government concept*. The use of digital technology enables the government to increase efficiency, transparency, and accountability in services, as well as respond to public issues more quickly, accurately, and in an integrated manner across sectors. One concrete example of the use of technology in public services is the implementation of the Single Emergency Call Number 112 service. In Indonesia, this service is regulated by Regulation of the Minister of Communication and Informatics of the Republic of Indonesia Number 10 of 2016, which confirms that the 112 service is a national system that can be accessed free of charge, 24 hours a day, and is integrated with various emergency response agencies. Thus, the 112 service functions as a coordination hub for handling emergency incidents, including social conflicts and security disturbances. In the context of regional government, the 112 service plays a strategic role as a public service system that is responsive to public reports. The success of its management depends heavily on institutional capacity, the quality of human resources, and the effectiveness of coordination between regional apparatuses and vertical agencies (KemenPAN-RB, 2020).

Based on the above description, this research is motivated by the reality of the increasing complexity of social conflicts in urban areas that require a swift and coordinated government presence. The 112 service in Manado City occupies a strategic position in handling conflicts based on public reports, but this role has not been fully studied in depth. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the role of the 112 service in handling conflicts based on public reports at the Manado City Communication and Informatics Office, so that it is expected to provide academic and practical contributions in strengthening public services and regional governance.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a qualitative approach chosen because it focuses on studies that position public services as a social process that occurs within the context of institutions, policies, and interactions between actors. The 112 service of the Manado City Communication and Informatics Office is not only understood as a technical means of handling public reports, but as a space for interaction between the state and citizens in situations that are often sensitive, urgent, and potentially conflict-prone. The qualitative approach allows researchers to explore how the 112 service policy is translated

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into daily practice, how bureaucratic officials respond to incoming conflict reports, and how cross-agency coordination is carried out under conditions that are not always ideal (Miles, Huberman, & Saldaña, 2019). This research was conducted at the Manado City Communication and Informatics Office, specifically at the unit that manages the 112 Emergency Call Single Number Service. The location was chosen based on the consideration that Manado City has complex social dynamics, making the 112 service an important instrument in managing conflicts based on public reports. Research informants were determined by *purposive sampling* and *snowball sampling*, including 112 service operators and *dispatchers*, officials and staff of the Communication and Information Service responsible for managing the 112 service, and other parties involved in handling public report-based conflicts such as social services, police, or BPBD according to the context of the report. Data collection techniques were carried out through semi-structured *in-depth* interviews, field observations of the 112 service work mechanism and the coordination process for handling conflict reports, as well as documentation of official documents, laws and regulations, archives, and relevant academic publications. Secondary data were obtained from documentary sources that supported the primary data analysis, including procedural guidelines, activity reports, and government policies related to public services and emergency call numbers. The research indicators are broken down into two main focuses with measurable sub-focuses. The first focus is the role of Service 112 in handling conflicts based on public reports, which is broken down into three sub-focuses: (1) Service 112's Response to Conflict Reports from the Community, with indicators of the report acceptance mechanism, the speed and accuracy of officer responses, the initial report verification process, and the clarity of information forwarded to the relevant agencies; (2) Service 112's Coordination Process in Following Up on Conflict Reports, with indicators of inter-agency communication patterns, division of roles and responsibilities (Service 112 as the reception and distribution center, technical agencies as field implementers), report distribution procedures, and the effectiveness of coordination in ensuring follow-up; (3) Service 112's Role in Controlling and Preventing the Escalation of Social Conflict, with indicators of its function as an early warning system, contribution in accelerating conflict handling, role in monitoring report follow-up, and impact on social stability and preventing conflict escalation in the community.

The second focus is the factors that influence the effectiveness of Service 112 in carrying out its role, which consists of five sub-focuses: (1) Institutional Aspects, with indicators of organizational structure, authority of Service 112, support of regional government policies, and institutional integration across agencies; (2) Human Resources, with indicators of officer competency (communication skills, accuracy, understanding of report classification), professionalism (responsive, neutral, unemotional attitude), and officer readiness to respond to reports quickly and appropriately; (3) Work Systems and Procedures, with indicators of implementation of Standard Operating Procedures (SOP), workflow for receiving, recording, verifying, and distributing reports, and the conformity between normative SOPs and implementation in the field; (4) Information Technology Support, with indicators of system speed in responding to reports in *real-time*, precision and accuracy of data recording, stability of IT infrastructure (network, application system), and system integration with related agencies; (5) Inter-agency coordination, with indicators of cross-agency communication patterns (Police, Satpol PP, BPBD, Health Service), synchronization of actions in handling reports, speed of response from receiving agencies, and effectiveness of coordination mechanisms in preventing conflict escalation.

Data analysis used an interactive model from Miles, Huberman, and Saldaña (2019) which consists of four stages: *data collection* (data collection through interviews, observation, documentation), *data condensation* (data selection, focusing, simplification, and transformation), *data display* (data presentation in the form of narrative text and tables), and *conclusion drawing/verifying* (drawing conclusions and verification). The analysis was carried out continuously from before entering the field until after the research was completed. Data validity was guaranteed through source triangulation (comparing information from various informants), method triangulation (comparing the results of interviews, observations, and documentation), inter-researcher triangulation (confirmation with other researchers in the same field), and time triangulation (data collection at different times to see the consistency of information). With this method, the research is expected to be able to answer the problem formulation comprehensively and produce recommendations for policy improvements based on empirical evidence to strengthen the role of Service 112 as an early warning system and instrument for preventing the escalation of social conflict in Manado City.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Role of Service 112 of the Manado City Communication and Information Service

1. 112 Service Response to Conflict Reports from the Community

The sub-focus of the 112 Service Response to Conflict Reports from the Public in this study shows that the 112 service plays a strategic role as the frontline in receiving public reports, particularly those related to social conflict. Data from the Manado City Communications and Information Office (2025) recorded 670 conflict reports, with the most common categories being disturbances to security and order (32.1%) and social conflicts between residents (22.1%). This reflects the high public demand for a fast and integrated complaint channel. From a public service perspective, Moenir (2010) states that service is the process of fulfilling needs through the activities of others, the results of which can be directly felt by the service recipient. The 112 service has demonstrated a relatively fast initial response: operators immediately record information and forward it to the relevant agency. However, research findings reveal that the response speed is not consistent across all stages, particularly in the process of forwarding reports and follow-up in the field. This inconsistency indicates that the response system is still more dominant at the receiving stage, while the subsequent stages still depend on the readiness of the receiving agency. This aligns with the SERVQUAL theory by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1988), which emphasizes that service quality is measured through the dimensions of *responsiveness* and *reliability*. Service 112 initially demonstrated good responsiveness, but reliability was not optimal due to variations in operator capabilities and workload dynamics.

In addition to speed, the verification and classification of reports is critical. Operators must ensure that the information received is clear, accurate, and categorized before forwarding it. However, time constraints and the high frequency of incoming reports simultaneously lead to potential inaccuracies in classifying conflict types and location details. This inaccuracy impacts field handling, as technical agencies rely heavily on the accuracy of initial information. Research by Turang and Palar (2022) on the Implementation of the Manado Siaga 112 Emergency Call Center Service also found that coordination constraints and resource constraints remain major obstacles, reinforcing these findings. Furthermore, Sumayku, Gosal, and Sampe (2022) in their study of public perceptions of the Manado Siaga 112 Service revealed that the public considered the service quite helpful, but there were still complaints regarding slow responses at certain times and a lack of follow-up on reports. This indicates that the responsiveness of the 112 Service has not fully met public expectations. Therefore, system strengthening, standardization of response protocols, and increased operator capacity are needed so that the 112 Service can function optimally as an early warning system for handling social conflicts in Manado City.

2. 112 Service Coordination Process in Following Up on Conflict Reports

The 112 Service's coordination process in following up on conflict reports indicates that this service is conceptually designed as a cross-agency coordination center. The communication pattern that occurs still relies heavily on direct communication between officers via telephone or other internal communication media. This condition indicates that the coordination system has not been fully integrated into a unified digital platform. According to Harijanti (2017), emergency services must be able to create fast, accurate, and integrated cross-agency coordination to prevent escalation of problems. In practice, the 112 Service has functioned as an initial information distribution center, but the effectiveness of coordination still depends heavily on the speed of individuals in conveying and receiving information. The *Collaborative Governance theory* of Ansell and Gash (2008) emphasizes that effective coordination requires shared rules, trust between parties, and a shared platform that facilitates transparent and rapid information exchange. Research findings indicate that coordination remains communicative and manual and does not yet reflect an automated emergency coordination system.

The division of roles and responsibilities between agencies has been normatively regulated: Service 112 serves as the center for receiving and distributing reports, while technical agencies (Police, Public Order Agency) act as implementers in the field. However, in its implementation, determining which agency handles a report often still depends on the operator's initial interpretation of the type of incident. This has the potential to lead to inconsistencies in report distribution. The report distribution procedure has been implemented through the stages of receipt, verification, and distribution, but the effectiveness of follow-up in the field still depends heavily on the response of each receiving agency. There is no unified operational standard that binds all parties to ensure uniformity and speed of handling. Research by Salsabilah and Arif (2025) on the implementation of Service 112 from an e-government perspective in Sidoarjo Regency also concluded that the effectiveness of conflict management is highly dependent on system integration, human resource capacity, and inter-agency coordination. This finding aligns with the results of research in Manado City. Therefore,

strengthening technology-based coordination systems and integrated SOPs is necessary to ensure the process of handling social conflicts through Service 112 can be more effective, rapid, and coordinated.

3. The Role of 112 Services in Controlling and Preventing the Escalation of Social Conflict

The role of the 112 Service in controlling and preventing the escalation of social conflict is a strategic function that is expected to become an early *warning system*. However, research findings indicate that the early detection function is still heavily dependent on direct reports from the public (reactive in nature), so that the role of the 112 Service as an *early warning system* is not yet optimal. Identification of potential conflicts is not yet supported by an active monitoring system or data analysis mechanisms capable of detecting potential conflicts before they actually occur or develop. From a crisis management perspective, Fink (1986) emphasized that conflict management should ideally go through the stages of early detection, rapid response, and systematic escalation control. The 112 Service is still in the initial response stage without the support of a strong *early warning system*, so the *conflict prevention function is not optimal*. The 112 Service's contribution to the initial handling of social conflicts is still limited to the function of forwarding information to relevant agencies. Although the report submission process has been carried out quickly by operators, the effectiveness in controlling conflict escalation is highly dependent on the speed and accuracy of the response of the receiving agency in the field. This indicates that the 112 Service's role is not entirely executive in the initial stages of handling, but rather remains predominantly as an information liaison. Lipsky's *Street-Level Bureaucracy Theory* (1980) explains that frontline officers often work with limited resources and ambiguous policies, so they tend to use individual discretion. In the context of the 112 Service, operators must make quick decisions in classifying reports and determining the destination agency, but without direct execution authority.

Furthermore, the cross-agency coordination process to prevent conflict escalation remains communicative and has not been fully integrated into a comprehensive control system. Coordination still relies heavily on direct communication between officers and manual monitoring by operators, thus lacking the support of a digital system capable of integrating all agencies into a single, unified platform. Consequently, the conflict management process is not yet automated, measurable, and sustainable. Research by Turang and Palar (2022) also found that the 112 service still faces challenges in cross-regional coordination, impacting the effectiveness of its handling. Thus, although the 112 service has played a significant role in the process of handling social conflicts, there remains a gap between the ideal concept and actual practice, particularly in the areas of early detection, initial handling, and coordination integration. Strengthening the *early warning system*, increasing the integration of information technology, and strengthening a more integrated coordination mechanism are necessary.

B. Factors Influencing the Effectiveness of Service 112 in Carrying Out Its Role

1. Institutional Aspects of L6*services 112

Institutional aspects are a fundamental factor influencing the effectiveness of the 112 Service. Research findings indicate that the established organizational structure is not yet fully capable of supporting optimal workload distribution. The workload still tends to be centered on operators as the frontline of 3333n, while coordinators and those in charge are not actively involved in the daily handling process. This condition indicates an imbalance in the implementation of the organizational structure. Dwiyanto (2019) stated that effective public services require an adaptive and results-oriented organizational structure. From the perspective of Performance Management Theory, an effective institution should be able to establish a clear division of labor system, performance targets, and evaluation mechanisms. However, the suboptimal distribution of workload reflects the weakness of the 112 Service institutional performance management system.

The limited authority of the 112 Service to receive, initial verification, and forward information—without direct execution authority in the field—causes the effectiveness of conflict management to be highly dependent on the response of external agencies such as the police and Public Order Agency (Satpol PP). This limited authority slows the handling process because coordination does not always occur simultaneously. From the perspective of the Public Service Responsiveness Theory, institutional effectiveness is largely determined by the organization's ability to respond quickly and appropriately to community needs. However, the limited authority of the 112 Service indicates that service responsiveness is not yet fully under the control of the system itself. Regional government policy support is in place, but its implementation has not been systematically integrated. The still manual coordination indicates that institutional innovation has not been accompanied by adaptive changes in work structures. As stated by the Indonesian Ministry of

Communication and Information (2019) in the concept of *smart governance*, emergency service institutions must be able to operate in an integrated and digital manner. Therefore, restructuring the distribution of workloads, expanding measurable authority, and strengthening binding regulations between agencies is necessary so that the institutional aspects of the 112 Service can support the effectiveness of social conflict management optimally.

2. Human Resources Services 112

Human resources (HR) are a key determinant of the effectiveness of the 112 Service. This study found that the competence and experience of operators are not evenly distributed. There is significant variation among operators in their ability to receive, record, and verify social conflict reports. Some officers are able to handle situations quickly and appropriately, while others still show difficulty in identifying the urgency of reports and formulating appropriate follow-up actions. This unevenness leads to inconsistencies in service quality. Becker's (1964) *Human Capital Theory* asserts that investment in education, training, and skills development will increase organizational productivity and performance. In the context of the 112 Service, investment in HR development is not optimal, as evidenced by the lack of robust and sustainable competency standardization. In addition to competence, the readiness and professionalism of officers also face challenges in dynamic working conditions. Officers are required to be on call 24/7 to respond to urgent, unscheduled reports. The dynamic nature of the high workload and situational pressures often leads to a decline in the consistency of professional attitudes. Some officers experience physical and mental fatigue, which impacts analytical acuity and decision-making speed. Lipsky (1980), in his *Street-Level Bureaucracy theory*, explains that frontline officers often work with limited resources and high workloads, thus tending to use individual discretion. Differences in ability between operators reflect the uneven use of discretion, which ultimately impacts service quality. Research by Sumayku, Gosal, and Sampe (2022) also revealed public complaints regarding slow responses and lack of follow-up on reports. These findings emphasize that the quality of 112 Service human resources directly influences public perceptions of the effectiveness of emergency services. Therefore, ongoing competency-based training programs, standardization through periodic competency tests, and balanced workload management are needed to maintain officer professionalism and work motivation.

3. 112 Service Work System and Procedures

The work systems and procedures outlined in Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) serve as the primary guide for operators in handling conflict reports. This study found that the implementation of SOPs is not entirely consistent across all operational conditions. Certain situations require operators to make rapid adjustments outside the ideal procedural flow, particularly when reports come in simultaneously or in emergency situations requiring an immediate response. This inconsistency leads to variations in the report handling process, potentially reducing service effectiveness. In his theory of ideal bureaucracy, Weber (1947) stated that public organizations require rational, standardized, and consistent procedures to achieve efficiency and accountability. However, the study findings indicate that the SOP for Service 112 does not fully reflect the ideal bureaucracy because there is still a gap between formal procedures and the reality on the ground.

The 112 Service workflow still requires high flexibility, indicating the limitations of SOPs in accommodating field dynamics. Existing SOPs are not yet fully capable of managing all the variations in conditions that occur in society, especially in handling complex and unpredictable social conflicts. As a result, operators often have to take the initiative to adjust work processes to remain responsive. This aligns with Lawrence and Lorsch's (1967) *Contingency Theory*, which states that organizational effectiveness depends on the alignment of internal structures (including SOPs) with external environmental demands. The dynamic and uncertain work environment of 112 Service demands high flexibility, yet existing SOPs remain rigid. Research by Salsabilah and Arif (2025) also found that the effectiveness of conflict management is highly dependent on system integration and the capacity of work procedures. Therefore, a comprehensive revision of SOPs is needed to include guidelines for handling special situations (*contingency procedures*), regular evaluations based on field results, and a clear definition of operator discretionary limits so that adjustments remain within the corridor of accountability.

4. Information Technology Support

Information technology (IT) support is the operational backbone of Service 112 as an early warning system. This study found that system and network disruptions remain a major obstacle affecting Service 112's response speed. The

stability of IT infrastructure is not yet fully optimal, resulting in delays in receiving and distributing social conflict reports under certain conditions. These disruptions not only reduce response speed but also potentially reduce the accuracy of emergency case handling. According to DeLone and McLean (2003) in their *Information Systems Success Model*, the success of an information system is determined by system quality, information quality, and service quality. If system and network quality are low, the overall effectiveness of the service will be compromised. This finding is in line with *Contingency Theory*, which emphasizes that organizational effectiveness depends on the compatibility of the technology used with the demands of a dynamic environment. Network instability causes Service 112 to not be fully adaptive to the demands of high speed and maximum reliability.

Furthermore, system integration with relevant agencies is also not yet optimal. Report distribution to the Police and Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) is still largely done manually and is not fully automated and integrated. This limited integration leads to inefficient inter-agency coordination, which slows down the resolution of social conflicts in the field. Kumar and van Dissel's (1996) *Interorganizational Information Systems theory* emphasizes the importance of inter-organizational system integration to ensure efficient coordination. For the 112 Service, the manual report distribution process indicates that system integration has not been optimally implemented. Research by Turang and Palar (2022) also found that resource constraints and coordination constraints are key obstacles. Therefore, increased investment in IT infrastructure, development of network redundancy systems, and integration of API- or *cloud-based platforms* that connect the 112 Service with all technical agencies in *real time* and automatically are needed.

5. Inter-agency coordination

Inter-agency coordination is a crucial factor in determining the effectiveness of the 112 Service. This study found that cross-agency coordination has not been fully integrated into an integrated communications system. Communication and synchronization of actions between agencies are still largely carried out manually via telephone or messaging applications, and are therefore not yet based on an automatically integrated system. This condition causes delays in the delivery of information and follow-up of social conflict reports. The *Collaborative Public Management theory* by Agranoff and McGuire (2001) explains that the successful implementation of complex public services requires inter-organizational collaboration involving various government agencies. Without effective coordination, the 112 Service will struggle to fulfill its role as a connecting node between the community and technical agencies.

The reliance on direct communication between officers makes effective coordination highly dependent on individual speed and capabilities, which are often inconsistent in emergency situations. Thomson and Perry (2006) in their *Collaboration Process Theory* explain that interorganizational collaboration often faces obstacles in the form of reliance on informal communication and a lack of structured formal mechanisms. In the 112 Service, the lack of a shared digital platform between agencies poses a risk of delays in the submission and follow-up of social conflict reports, potentially increasing the risk of conflict escalation in the community. Research by Salsabilah and Arif (2025) also confirms that the effectiveness of conflict management is highly dependent on system integration and inter-agency coordination. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a formal coordination protocol that is binding on all agencies through joint decisions or memorandums of understanding (MoUs), develop an integrated communication platform, and conduct regular joint coordination simulation training (*joint exercises*) to improve synchronized actions in emergency situations. With integrated coordination, the 112 Service can function as an effective crisis command center in ensuring social stability and minimizing the potential for conflict in Manado City.

CONCLUSION

1. The role of the 112 Service remains reactive, facilitative, and suboptimal. Of the 670 conflict reports received, the initial response was quite good but inconsistent across all stages. Coordination with relevant agencies still relies on manual communication and has not been integrated into a digital platform. The early warning *system* has not been proactive, thus its role in controlling and preventing conflict escalation is not optimal.

2. Factors that influence the effectiveness of the 112 Service include five main aspects:

- Institutional: The organizational structure does not yet support optimal workload distribution; authority is limited to receiving and forwarding reports, without direct execution.
- Human Resources: Operator competency is not evenly distributed, readiness and professionalism are decreasing due to high workloads for 24 hours.
- Work Systems and Procedures: SOPs have not been consistently implemented, are less adaptive to field dynamics, forcing operators to make adjustments outside of procedures.

- Information Technology Support: Network and system disruptions still occur frequently, integration with related agencies is not yet automatic and integrated.
- Inter-agency Coordination: Still manual via telephone/text messages, no shared digital platform yet, causing potential delays in response.

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